

Investigations on the Himalayan Bryophytes : Pinguisane sesquiterpenoids from *Porella densifolia* (Steph.) Hatt.

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The terpenoid composition of *Porella densifolia* (Steph.) Hatt., a liverwort, has been determined. Of more than 60 components in the steam volatile oil, 35 components constituting 95.4% of the extract have been identified. It is characterized by the dominant presence of pinguisane type sesquiterpenoids such as norpinguisone methyl ester (46.6%) and norpinguisone (4.6%) besides striatene (11.8%) and bicyclogermacrene (11.6%). In addition, twentytwo compounds are being reported for the first time in *P. densifolia*. This is the first screening report of the terpenoid composition of *P. densifolia* (Steph.) Hatt. from Kumaun (North Western Himalaya) which differs from the previous two reports on the materials from Japan and Punjab with respect to major as well as minor chemical constituents.

The *Porella* species of the liverworts are rich source of sesqui- and diterpenoids which show interesting biological properties such as antimicrobial activity, inhibition of germination of higher plants, antifeedant and antitumour activities¹. The liverworts occasionally produce their own unique constituents : the pinguisane- and the sacculatane-type terpenoids which have not been found in higher plants, fungi or marine organisms². There are two types of *Porella* species : pungent and non-pungent. The former produces the intensively pungent drimane-polygodial and related compounds along with pinguisanes. The non-pungent type does not produce polygodial but usually are rich in pinguisanes and contain perrottetianals³. The most significant biochemical property in hepaticae is that they elaborate the optically opposite isomeric sesquiterpenoids to those found in higher plants, although there are some exceptions⁴.

P. densifolia (Porellaceae) belongs to the order Jungermanniales and has turpentine-like smell. Not much has been done on its chemical composition. There are only two reports on the GC-MS of its extracts which showed the presence of pinguisane derivatives along with few other terpenoids⁵. Although, Himalaya harbour a variety of bryophytes in different ecological conditions, Indian bryophytes are yet to be attempted for their systematic chemical investigation more so on Himalayan species. The present communication on the essential oil of *P. densifolia* (Steph.) Hatt. is an attempt in this direction.

Results and Discussion

The GC showed the presence of more than 60 compounds, out of which 35 compounds constituting 95.4% of the total oil have been identified (Table 1). The analysis revealed that the oil was exceptionally dominated by sesquiterpenoids ($\approx 93.0\%$). Pinguisane derivatives were the major constituents (51.6%) of the oil. The oil contained

norpinguisone methyl ester (46.6%) as the major constituent followed by striatene (11.8%), bicyclogermacrene (11.6%) and norpinguisone (4.6%). In addition, 22 compounds are being reported for the first time in *P. densifolia*. In earlier reports on the extracts of *P. densifolia* subsp. *appendiculata* from Punjab and Japanese *P. densifolia* var. *fallax* material, 18-hydroxykauren-15-one was reported as one of the major components but it was not detected in our Himalayan material. Also, caespitene constituting $\approx 2.0\%$ of the present sample, was not present in the earlier reports.

Table 1. Composition of the essential oil of *Porella densifolia* (Steph.) Hatt.*

Sl. no.	Content % Oil	Kovat Index (DB-5)	Compound
1.	0.22	0929	α -Pinene
2.	0.38	0943	Camphene
3.	0.17	-	Bicyclo-elemene
4.	0.11	-	Isomer of caespitene
5.	0.10	1347	α -Cubebene
6.	0.52	-	Solina-4(14), 7(11)-diene
7.	0.10	1381	β -Elemene
8.	0.74	1404	<i>ent</i> - α -Gurjunene
9.	3.60	1406	<i>ent</i> -z-Caryophyllene
10.	1.75	-	Caespitene
11.	0.49	1450	α -Humulene
12.	0.45	1455	Clovene
13.	3.34	-	Isomer of striatene
14.	11.76	-	Striatene
15.	0.42	1486	β -Selinene
16.	11.61	1499	<i>ent</i> -Bicyclogermacrene
17.	0.25	1506	<i>ent</i> - β -Bisabolene
18.	t	1510	<i>ent</i> -Cubebol
19.	0.19	1560	Ledol

Table-I (contd.)

20.	0.10	-	Deoxopinguisone
21.	1.06	1580	ent-Spathulenol
22.	2.69	1586	ent-Caryophyllene oxide
24.	0.81	1635	ent- γ -Eudesmol
25.	0.91	1661	Patchouli alcohol
26.	t	1696	Norsecoswartzianin
27.	0.40	1706	Pinguisone
28.	t	-	Isodrimeninol
29.	t	1760	Drimenol
30.	46.58	1766	Norpinguisone methyl ester
31.	t	1797	Caespitenone
32.	0.44	-	ent-Kaur-15-ene
33.	0.22	2046	ent-Kaur-16-ene
34.	0.96	-	ent-Kaur-16-en-7 α ,15 β -diol
35.	1.17	-	Perrottetianal A

* The stereochemistry of compounds 8, 9, 16, 17, 18, 21, 22, 24, 32, 33 and 34 was tentatively assigned on the basis of compounds reported previously in *Porella* species.

t = trace quantity.

Diterpenoids constituted about 6.3% of the present oil sample. The most abundant among them is perrottetianal A (1.2%), a pungent sacculatane type diterpene aldehyde which is biologically active and was not reported earlier in *P. densifolia*. The presence of perrottetianal A and absence of polygodial suggested that the present sample belonged to non-pungent type of *Porella* species.

Thus, the *P. densifolia* (Steph.) Hatt. from North Western Himalaya (Kumaun) differs significantly in chemical constitution from the previous reports from Japan and Punjab, with respect to major as well as minor terpenoid constituents.

Experimental

P. densifolia (Steph.) Hatt. was collected from Eber foyle forest (2200 m) Nainital, Kumaun, during the month October. The essential oil was obtained by steam distillation of the plant. The GC and GC-MS analysis was done using fused silica capillary column (30 m \times 0.25 mm) DB-5 with helium as carrier gas in a Hewlett-Packard 5840 A GC interfaced with Hewlett-Packard 5985 mass spectrophotometer. The column temperature was programmed at 3 $^{\circ}$ /min from 60 to 240 $^{\circ}$. The mass spectra corresponding to GC peaks were scanned to 70 eV under EI condition. The CC (silica gel; hexane : ether as eluent) and HPLC (μ -Porasil column : 300 \times 7.8 mm) gave three compounds whose MS, IR, ^1H nmr, ^{13}C nmr and ^1H - ^1H COSY were taken. Identification of remaining constituents was done by comparing their Kovat indices.

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References

1. Y. Asakawa, "Progress in the Chemistry of Organic Natural Products", Springer, Wien, New York, 1995, Vol. 95, p. 464.
2. M. Toyota, F. Nagashima, K. Shima and Y. Asakawa, *Phytochemistry*, 1992, 31, 183.
3. F. Nagashima, H. Izumo, A. Ishimaru, S. Momasaki, M. Toyota, T. Hashimoto and Y. Asakawa, *Phytochemistry*, 1996, 43, 1285.
4. Y. Asakawa, M. Toyota and T. Takemoto, *Phytochemistry*, 1981, 20, 257.
5. Y. Asakawa, K. Takikawa, M. Toyota, A. Ueda, M. Tori and S. S. Kumar, *Phytochemistry*, 1987, 26, 1019.